

CHARACTERIZATION OF PERSONAL EXPOSURE TO PARTICULATE MATTER OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL IN THE SANTANDER BAY (NORTHERN SPAIN)

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Exposure to particulate matter (PM) negatively affects human health. The PM toxicity mechanisms seem to be related to the ability of certain PM components to modify the balance between oxidants and antioxidants and to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), triggering inflammatory responses in the organisms. A metric that can represent this toxicity mechanism has been developed in recent years, the so-called PM oxidative potential (PM OP). Although many OP studies have been recently published, most of these assess the PM OP exposure by stationary samplers. A better characterization of PM exposure may be made by personal samplers, which account for indoor/outdoor activities (Expósito et al., 2021). Personal sampling can be incorporated into epidemiological studies to assess the impact of PM OP exposure on health, mainly in vulnerable groups such as people having respiratory diseases.

With this aim, the ASTHMA-FENOP project was planned. Asthmatic (n=44) and control (n=37) subjects living in the Santander bay (northern Spain) were recruited to wear PM personal samplers (SKC PMI coarse) for 24 h and to determine systemic (interleukin 6 and 10) and respiratory (fractional exhaled nitric oxide (FENO)) inflammatory biomarkers. Santander bay was selected for this study because previous studies reported relatively high levels of some transition metals active in OP assays, such as Mn and Fe (Hernández-Pellón and Fernández-Olmo, 2019).

PM10-2.5 and PM2.5 filters were collected from each volunteer and delivered to the laboratory for freezing until OP analysis. Two OP assays were carried out, measuring the depletion of two antioxidants; dithiothreitol (DTT), and ascorbic acid (AA). The OP-DTT and OP-AA values were calculated from the slope of AA/DTT concentration vs time curves, and were expressed per m³ of inhaled air (nmol/min/m³). In this work, only PM OP results are presented.

Overall, 81 volunteers participated in the study. The PM OP results are shown in Table 1 for both size fractions.

Table 1. PM OP of personal samples (nmol/min/m³): arithmetic mean of asthmatic/control subjects

OP-DTTv	OP-AAv	OP-DTTv	OP-AAv
PM10-2.5	PM10-2.5	PM2.5	PM2.5
0.21/0.13	0.80/0.17	0.33/0.17	0.99/0.34

The order of magnitude of personal OP values were similar to that found in a previous study, where two

stationary PM samplers were used, one near the main metal industrial emitter (a Mn alloy production plant) and the other one in an urban background site (University campus at Santander). However, although the former study showed higher OP values in the urban-industrial site respect to the urban site, the personal sampling campaign did not show site differences, as depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Map of PM OP (nmol/min/m³) and residence of volunteers.

To conclude, personal exposure did not show a spatial pattern of PM OP, probably due to the contribution of indoor and occupational exposure to personal OP values, contrary to OP studies with stationary samplers, which only account for outdoor exposure.

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